

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: This article presents the current problems and laws of introducing innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process.

Key words: continuity and integrity, education, scientific, technical and advanced technological achievements, socio-economic, political, humanitarian knowledge.

The future of every society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. Today, reforming and improving the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies to it, and increasing the effectiveness of education have been raised to the level of state policy. With the adoption of the Law “On Education” and the “National Program of Personnel Training”, the basis of modern personnel training was created through the continuous education system.

It is known that continuity and integrity put an end to excessive repetition in the education system, first of all, it expands the moral and intellectual potential of the society, and, moreover, it ensures the stable development of production as a factor of improving the social and scientific-technical development of the state. During the development of pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, everyone has the opportunity to strengthen their professional training and skills.

Continuing education consists of a perfect combination of various forms, methods, means, methods and directions of providing deep, all-round basic education and training of specialist personnel. The quality of continuing education is ensured by the interrelationship between various components, the rational application of certain methods and techniques to the educational process.

The general pedagogical and didactic requirement for all stages of education is to improve the effectiveness of independent work on the basis of programming knowledge, imagination and skills of the student (or pupil), to

increase his interest in scientific thinking and academic subjects, to deepen his professional knowledge, theoretical and practical is to increase their activity during training. The world pedagogical experience confirms that modern pedagogical technologies have unlimited opportunities to interest students (or students) in science and increase their activity in independent work.

Today's task of education is to teach students to be able to operate independently in the conditions of the information-educational environment that is growing day by day, to use the flow of information wisely[1]. For this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent work. The implementation of the "National Personnel Training Program" will lead to fundamental reforms in the structure and content of the continuing education system based on modern scientific achievements and social experience. For this, first of all, it is necessary to provide the educational process in all forms of the educational system with advanced, scientific and methodologically based new and modern methodology. Effective use of the achievements of science, technology and advanced technology according to the purpose, tasks, content, and methodical requirements of educating the young generation is one of the urgent problems facing today's education system.

As a producer of educational services, a person participates in the transfer of knowledge and experience to a student (or pupil), in the conditions of the material production environment, as well as in the fields of science, culture and service provision. For this reason, one of the established tasks of education is to provide high-level education and train qualified personnel based on modern educational programs. An educational institution creates educational conditions for a growing person in the process of training. Oriented formation and development of students' (or students') knowledge needs and abilities increases the responsibility of the teacher's activity. The qualification of a teacher of an educational institution should have two sides, illuminated by special and pedagogical sciences, and he should always ask: "Why should we teach?", "How should we teach?" should find answers to the questions, as well as be based on knowledge that takes into account the characteristics of education[2].

Young pedagogues should acquire pedagogical and psychological knowledge, technology and teaching methods as they enter the educational process in addition to their existing knowledge of the specialty. Taking this into account, the main issues in improving the qualifications of young pedagogues are determined as follows:

- formation of pedagogical skills that ensure the effectiveness of the teaching process;
- formation of a new professional mindset aimed at understanding socio-economic, political, humanitarian knowledge;
- mastering the system of pedagogical knowledge as the methodological basis of the teacher's activity;
- mastering the teaching technology as a method system that is closer to the professional activities of teachers[3].

This program was developed in order to create the above-mentioned qualifications and skills in young talented pedagogues and scientific personnel currently working in educational institutions. The main goal is to teach modern pedagogical technologies to the young promising pedagogues working in the educational institutions of our republic, to further strengthen their knowledge of pedagogy and psychology, and to teach them to apply their knowledge to the educational process, as well as to teach them is to reveal the secrets of pedagogical skills.

References:

1. Ochilov M. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. - Qarshi; Nasaf, 2000.
2. Ishmuhamedov R. Innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari. - T., Nizomiy nomidagi TDU, 2009.
3. G'aniyeva M. Nazariy va amaliy o'quv mashg'ulotlarda o'qitish texnologiyalari to'plami. - T, TDIU, Iqtisodiyot. 2013.
4. Sobirovich T. B. et al. Strategy of spiritual renewal in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – T. 24. – №. 6. – C. 3084-3089.
5. Sobirovich T. B. Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST). – 2023. – T. 7. – №. 1. – C. 149-157.
6. Sobirovich T. B., Norman Z. D. M. Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan //Harmony. – 2023. – T. 7. – №. 1. – C. 08-16.
7. Sobirovich T. B. MANIFESTATION OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE IDEOSPHERE OF UZBEKISTAN //Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects (Spain). – 2023. – C. 89-92.
8. Sobirovich T. B. Uzbekistan is a Country of International Harmony and Religious Tolerance //Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences. – 2022. – C. 32-35.
9. Sobirovich T. B., Ikrom o'g'li I. M. ISSUE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY IN THE VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS.

10. Sobirovich T. B. Uzbekistan: from national revival to national progress //Modern scientific challenges and trends. – 2020. – №. 27. – С. 5.
11. Sobirovich T. B. Spiritual renewal and interethnic relations in the Strategy of Actions //Теория і практика сoвременной науки. Rossiya, Saratov. – 2018. – №. 3. – С. 33.
12. Turdiyev B. Behbudi's views on the spiritual renewal of society //Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.

